

BLOOM Data Management Plan

Version 1

Description

BLOOM aims to explore the citation and disciplinary nature of Italian science. As such this data management plan will handle the necessary data from IRIS, OpenCitation and additional datasets needed to perform this research.

Funder

Grant

Researchers

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Organizations

Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: BLOOM Data Management Plan

Description:

BLOOM aims to explore the citation and disciplinary nature of Italian science. As such this data management plan will handle the necessary data from IRIS, OpenCitation and additional datasets needed to perform this research.

Researchers:

Maryam Dadrasrazi (0009-0005-9585-5662)

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Tianchi Yang (0009-0006-6945-0781)

Sara Roggiani (0009-0006-7981-6652)

Miriana Pinto (0009-0002-8935-5512)

Organizations:

Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna

Contact: Manyara Regina (regina.wkmanyara@gmail.com)

2. Funding

Funding organizations:

Grants:

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

IRIS to Open Citations Mapper

This object contains the scholarly information available in both IRIS and Open Citations for 6 Italian institutions. The dataset is divided into six files, one for each institution and each with two files: `iris_oc_meta` (which contains the scholarly metadata for the publications) and `iris_oc_index` (which contains the citation information for the publications).

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Andreose, Erica	0009-0003-7124-9639	erica.andreose@uni-bo.it	University of Bologna

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
Heibi, Ivan	0009-0003-7124-9639	ivan.heibi2@uni-bo.it	University of Bologna	Creator
Peroni, Silvio	0000-0003-	silvio.peroni@u	University of	Creator

	0530-4305	nibo.it	Bologna	
Zilli, Leonardo	0009-0007-4127-4875	leonardo.zilli@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

University of Bologna

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

For this information, refer to the original Data Management Plan of the dataset (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

Yes

2.1.2 Re-using an existing dataset: why and how

We made use of this dataset for the analysis of scholarly citations in Italy as it provided the required data to answer the project's research questions.

The dataset has the CC0 license making it freely available for our research purposes.

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

iris_in_oc

2.2.2 Data types

- a. textual
- b. born digital
- c. derived
- d. qualitative

2.2.3 Data formats

- a. csv
- b. json

2.2.4 Size of data

gigabytes (GB)

Comment:

4

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

The full process of data generation and collection is described in the reference DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

2.2.7 Dataset description

The dataset contains several folders, one for each university involved. Each folder contains the following sub-directories:

- iris_in_oc_meta contains basic bibliographic information of the IRIS publication recognised in OpenCitations Meta;
- iris_in_oc_index contains all the citations extracted from OpenCitations Index that involve any of the IRIS publications included in iris_in_oc_meta;
- iris_no_pid contains basic bibliographic information of the IRIS publications that do not specify any of the PIDs (i.e. DOI, PMID, ISBN) necessary for mapping them with the entries in OpenCitations Meta;
- iris_not_in_meta contains basic bibliographic information for IRIS publications with the requested PIDs that were not recognised in OpenCitations Meta.

In addition, the archive contains two additional files:

- logs, which contains the printed logs of the process executed to obtain the aforementioned data;
- Mapping_IRIS_MIUR.xlsx, which maps the IRIS publication types with the national categories defined by the Italian Ministry of University and Research.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18202530	No	No	Generalist

4.1.3 Further information on long-term preservation strategy

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18202530

4.2.2 Metadata

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

4.2.3 Keywords

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

The dataset can be accessed on Zenodo at the following link:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18202530>.

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's

bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/>

4.5.2 Documentation

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

5.2.2 Backup

For this information, refer to the original DMP of the dataset (Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & Di Marzo, S. (2025). DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's

bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5 (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761351>).

Map of Italian Science Intermediate and Final datasets

This dataset collection comprises all output files produced by the BLOOM Map of Italian Science workflow, which maps the international reach of Italian academic research by linking IRIS publication records from six Italian universities with OpenCitations, OpenAIRE and ROR data. It includes the intermediate mapping outputs of the pipeline — IRIS publications enriched with OpenCitations persistent identifiers (DOI, PMID, ISBN) and citation pairs, a crosswalk between OpenAIRE organizations and their ROR identifiers and countries, and a mapping of IRIS publications to OpenAIRE organizations via author affiliations — together with the final per-university citation-count tables for incoming and outgoing citation relationships, aggregated by both partner organization and partner country. Collectively, these datasets answer the project's core research question of which institutions and countries cite, or are cited by, each university's OpenCitations-indexed IRIS publications, and form the basis for the country-level, organization-level and combined visual analyses developed as part of the BLOOM project.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Barbato, Tommaso	0009-0007-0093-4304	tommaso.barbato@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
D'amelio, Nicol	0009-0004-8197-6255	nicol.damelio@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator
Pinto, Miriana	0009-0002-8935-5512	mariana.pinto@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator
Roggiani, Sara	0009-0006-7981-6652	sara.roggiani2@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator
Dadrasrazi, Maryam	0009-0005-9585-5662	maryam.dadrasrazi@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator
Yu, Peize	0009-0004-5394-4264	peize.yu@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

University of Bologna

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

FAIR compliance is built into the pipeline design at no extra cost: each processing step automatically generates accompanying metadata files (row counts, runtime info, provenance), outputs use open formats (CSV, JSON), and code, protocols and final datasets are made openly available via GitHub, protocols.io and Zenodo, ensuring findability and accessibility without separate curation effort.

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

No

2.1.3 Creating a new dataset

The dataset is original as there was no other available dataset specifically addressing the research question. While IRIS, OpenCitations, OpenAIRE and ROR each provide valuable source data individually, none of them offers a ready-made mapping that links Italian IRIS publications to the specific institutions and countries that cite or are cited by them. Producing this dataset therefore requires integrating and cross-referencing these four existing sources through a dedicated pipeline, as no equivalent pre-existing dataset addresses this institution- and country-level citation mapping for Italian research output.

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

BLOOM Map of Italian Science Data

2.2.2 Data types

- a. born digital
- b. quantitative
- c. processed
- d. numerical
- e. textual

2.2.3 Data formats

a. csv

b. json

c. txt

2.2.4 Size of data

gigabytes (GB)

Comment:

7.6GB compressed, 40GB uncompressed

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

The dataset is generated by cross-referencing bibliographic metadata from six Italian IRIS instances with OpenCitations Meta, OpenAIRE Graph and ROR data (IRIS publications v1.1.0, Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18202530>; ROR Data v2.7, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>; OpenCitations Meta CSV v2026-01-14, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>; OpenAIRE Graph v10.6.0, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17725827>). The process involves enriching IRIS citation pairs with OpenCitations PIDs, mapping OpenAIRE organizations to ROR identifiers and countries, resolving publications to their authors' affiliated organizations via OpenAIRE relations, and aggregating these into per-university incoming/outgoing citation counts by organization and country. Data provenance is maintained by documenting the specific dump versions used, recording metadata and checkpoint files at each pipeline stage, and version-controlling the Python-based transformation scripts via GitHub.

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

The data is generated as part of the BLOOM project to map the international reach of Italian academic research, addressing the research question of which institutions and countries cite, or are cited by, the IRIS publications of six Italian universities as indexed in OpenCitations. By combining IRIS, OpenCitations, OpenAIRE and ROR data, the project produces per-university citation-count tables aggregated by organization and by country, for both incoming and outgoing citation relationships, enabling analysis of institutional and geographical citation patterns and asymmetries (e.g., whether institutions act primarily as citation receivers or citation consumers).

Within the project's scope, the data feeds three Jupyter notebooks analyzing country-level, organization-level and combined citation patterns, and underpins the findings published in the article "In the World of Citations, Are We Really Open(Minded), or Stuck in a Comfort Zone?", which additionally extends the analysis to scholarly disciplinary flows. Beyond the project, the dataset and accompanying code are released openly (Zenodo, GitHub, protocols.io) to support reuse by other researchers interested in citation network analysis, open science metrics, or the international visibility of national research systems, and to feed a complementary website (<https://open-sci.github.io/2025-2026/>) offering interactive visualizations and a narrative presentation of the findings.

2.2.7 Dataset description

The BLOOM Map of Italian Science dataset provides per-university citation-count mappings between the IRIS publications of six Italian institutions and the global organizations and countries that cite or are cited by them, as indexed in OpenCitations. It was generated by combining timestamped data dumps from IRIS publications (v1.1.0), OpenCitations Meta (v2026-01-14), OpenAIRE Graph (v10.6.0) and ROR (v2.7), streamed and cross-referenced through a dedicated Python pipeline.

For each institution, the dataset identifies and quantifies incoming and outgoing citation relationships through four CSV outputs: citation counts by citing/cited organization, and the same counts aggregated by country, alongside accompanying metadata files documenting row counts and processing statistics. Developed to map the international reach of Italian academic research, this resource highlights the organizational and geographical partners most engaged with the Italian academic system, distinguishing institutions that primarily receive citations from those that primarily cite external work.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.2.2 Legal issues: description and solutions

No legal issues were identified.

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

No contractual, legal or regulatory restrictions apply, as all source data (IRIS, OpenCitations, OpenAIRE, ROR) and the resulting outputs are openly licensed. The final dataset deposited on Zenodo (~7.6GB compressed, ~40GB uncompressed) — comprising the per-university citation-count tables and organization/country mappings — is modest in size and can be preserved in its entirety, with no selection necessary.

The much larger raw and intermediate data generated during processing (the ~350GB of input dumps, including ~280GB from OpenAIRE, plus intermediate mapping files such as iris_oc_pids and omid_organizations.json) are not retained long-term, since they are easily replicable: the source dumps are already permanently archived with their own DOIs on Zenodo, and the intermediate files can be regenerated by rerunning the version-controlled pipeline scripts against those same dumps.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
Open Science 2025-26	https://github.com/	No	No	Generalist

	open-sci/2025-2026			
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Comment:

The long-term preservation strategy relies on two complementary, persistent repositories. All processing scripts and Jupyter notebooks (build_iris_oc_pids.py, match_organizations_countries.py, resolve_pids_organizations.py, count_citations.py, plus the visualization and validation code) are version-controlled and preserved in the project's GitHub repository (<https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026/>), ensuring the full processing pipeline remains accessible, inspectable and re-executable independently of the original infrastructure. The detailed step-by-step methodology is additionally preserved as a versioned protocol on protocols.io (BLOOM Map of Italian Science Protocol v.3, <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm86kbg3p/v3>), documenting exact commands, dump versions and parameters used. The final datasets are deposited on Zenodo under a CC-BY 4.0 license with a persistent DOI (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20691555>), guaranteeing long-term accessibility and citability independent of GitHub, while an accompanying README.md documents the structure and content of all preserved files.

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20691555

4.2.2 Metadata

The dataset is deposited on Zenodo, which assigns a persistent DOI and uses the DataCite metadata schema (InvenioRDM), ensuring compliance with recognized, interoperable metadata standards and indexing in OpenAIRE. The record's metadata includes title, authors with ORCID identifiers, institutional affiliation with ROR identifier (University of Bologna), publication date, version, license (CC-BY

4.0), keywords (OpenCitations, OpenAIRE, ROR, IRIS, Open Science, etc.), resource type, and a descriptive abstract outlining the dataset's content and structure.

In addition to repository-level metadata, the dataset is accompanied by process-level documentation: each pipeline stage produces dedicated `*.metadata.json` files recording runtime, row counts, match statistics and output sizes, and an accompanying README.md describes the content and structure of all files in the deposited dataset (organized into the map_of_italian_science` and disciplinary_flow` folders). The full processing protocol, including data sources, versions and transformation steps, is further documented and versioned on protocols.io (https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm86kbg3p/v3).`

4.2.3 Keywords

OpenCitations, OpenAIRE, ROR, IRIS, Open Science, DOAJ, Scimago, LoC

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

The research output is openly available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20691555>) under a CC-BY 4.0 license, with no access restrictions. The accompanying processing code is openly available on GitHub (<https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026/>), and the detailed methodology is published on protocols.io.

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

The full methodology is described in detail in the published protocol "BLOOM Map of Italian Science Protocol v.3" (<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm86kbg3p/v3>), which documents each stage of the data lifecycle: download and preparation of the source dumps (IRIS, ROR, OpenCitations Meta, OpenAIRE Graph), the four-stage Python

processing pipeline (PID mapping, organization-to-ROR/country mapping, publication-to-organization resolution, citation counting), and the subsequent data validation and visualization steps carried out via Jupyter notebooks. Following this shared, versioned protocol across all stages ensures methodological consistency, reproducibility and interoperability with related work building on the same source datasets.

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

The dataset relies on established persistent identifier (PID) schemas as its core controlled vocabularies for entity identification: DOI and PMID for publications, ISBN for monographs, OMID for OpenCitations' internal identifiers, ROR IDs for research organizations, and ORCID for author identification. These PIDs ensure that institutions, publications and authors are unambiguously identified and interoperable with other systems using the same standards.

For relationships between entities, the OpenAIRE Graph's controlled relation vocabulary is used, specifically the `hasAuthorInstitution` and `isAuthorInstitutionOf` relation types, which formally express author-affiliation links between publications and organizations. Country information follows the naming and coding conventions provided by ROR (with OpenAIRE's own country field as fallback), supporting consistent geographic aggregation.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Comment:

The dataset is released under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0), as indicated on the Zenodo deposit (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20691555>). This is a standard, machine-readable license that allows unrestricted reuse, redistribution and adaptation of the data, provided appropriate credit is given to the original authors.

4.5.2 Documentation

The dataset is accompanied by a README.md file describing the content and structure of all files. Each pipeline stage additionally produces dedicated

`*.metadata.json` files documenting runtime, row counts and processing statistics for that step, providing machine-readable provenance documentation alongside the human-readable README.

The full processing methodology, including data sources, versions, parameters and step-by-step procedures, is documented separately in the versioned protocol "BLOOM Map of Italian Science Protocol v.3" on protocols.io (<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm86kbg3p/v3>). The software required to generate and reproduce the dataset is open source and made available, together with its own documentation, in the project's GitHub repository (<https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026/>), referenced from the dataset's metadata, and on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20718139>).

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

Data quality is ensured by separating unresolved records into dedicated missing-data files at each pipeline stage, normalizing and deduplicating identifiers (DOI, PMID, ROR ID) before aggregation, and generating metadata files with row counts and match statistics for every step. A dedicated validation.py script checks the processed datasets before they're used in the visualization notebooks, and the standardized protocol on protocols.io ensures consistent, reproducible processing across all six institutions.

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

During the active phase of the project, code and intermediate processing scripts are stored and version-controlled on GitHub (<https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026/>), which tracks all changes, contributions and access through standard repository permissions and commit history, supporting collaborative development among the project team. Given the size of the raw data dumps (~350GB), these are kept on local storage during processing rather than in the code repository, and are

not retained long-term since they remain permanently archived with their own DOIs on Zenodo.

Once finalized, the output dataset is deposited on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20691555>), which provides persistent, openly accessible storage with no access restrictions, version tracking, and a fixed DOI ensuring the data remains retrievable independently of the active project infrastructure.

5.2.2 Backup

Source code, processing scripts and notebooks are backed up through GitHub's distributed version control, which preserves the full commit history and allows recovery of any previous state in case of accidental loss or corruption. The raw source dumps (IRIS, OpenCitations, OpenAIRE, ROR) are not separately backed up locally, since they are permanently archived with their own DOIs on Zenodo and can be re-downloaded if needed. The final output dataset itself is preserved on Zenodo, a repository with its own redundant storage and backup infrastructure, ensuring recovery is guaranteed independently of the project team's local systems.

5.2.3 Additional security

No additional security is required as the data processed is not sensitive and has been made open and publicly accessible on Zenodo.

Software for fetching and combining data for research question

1a

This software is used to parse and iterate the CSV datasets of the IRIS institutional repositories and to stream and process large local data dumps from OpenCitations, OpenAIRE, and ROR in order to retrieve and combine data for the research question. Rather than querying live API endpoints, the pipeline operates entirely on offline bulk exports (~350GB total), streaming tar.gz archives directly without intermediate extraction to disk, in order to link IRIS publication records to citation metadata, affiliated organizations, and countries of origin.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Barbato, Tommaso	0009-0007-0093-4304	tommaso.barbato@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
D'Amelio, Nicol	0009-0004-8197-6255	nicol.damelio@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator

Roggiani, Sara	0009-0006-7981-6652	sara.roggiani2@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator
Pinto, Miriana	0009-0002-8935-5512	miriana.pinto@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator
Dadrasrazi, Maryam	0009-0005-9585-5662	maryam.dadrasrazi@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator
Yu, Peize	0009-0004-5394-4264	peize.yu@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

University of Bologna

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

Data management will be handled directly by the research team as part of normal research activity. Code is versioned on GitHub under an open license, ensuring transparency and reusability. Input datasets are drawn exclusively from open, publicly accessible sources (OpenCitations, OpenAIRE, ROR, IRIS). Output datasets will be deposited in an open repository (e.g. Zenodo) with accompanying metadata and documentation, making them Findable and Accessible. The use of standard, non-proprietary formats (CSV, JSON) and openly documented processing scripts ensures Interoperability and Reusability in line with FAIR principles.

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Software

2 Summary

2.3 Identification of software

2.3.1 Are you re-using already existing software?

No

2.3.3 Creating new software

No existing tool handles the specific combination of data sources and research question addressed here. The pipeline must ingest and cross-reference heterogeneous bulk dumps (IRIS institutional CSVs, the OpenCitations Meta archive, OpenAIRE publication and relation exports, and the ROR dump) each with distinct formats and schemas, at a scale (~350GB) that requires streaming processing without full extraction to disk. The linking logic, citation direction tracking, and organization-to-country resolution are all specific to the research design and cannot be achieved by repurposing generic bibliometric or data-wrangling tools.

2.4 Software characteristics

2.4.1 Software name

map_of_italian_science

2.4.2 Type of software

Information management and manipulation

2.4.3 Software formats

.py for the core scripts

2.4.4 Size of software

kilobytes (KB)

Comment:

500

2.4.5 How is software created/used

Software is manually coded in Python 3.13 and versioned on GitHub so that all changes are tracked and the full development history is preserved. The pipeline

consists of four sequential standalone scripts, each reading the outputs of the previous stage. Scripts are designed to be idempotent (they skip already-completed work and support checkpoint/resume for long-running stages) so they can be re-executed safely if interrupted. Once the pipeline has been run to completion on the full dataset, its outputs are considered the research data.

2.4.6 Why is the software created/used

The software is created to process and cross-reference large heterogeneous bulk data dumps from multiple open scholarly infrastructure sources (IRIS, OpenCitations, OpenAIRE, ROR), produce intermediate outputs at each pipeline stage, and generate the final aggregated citation counts, in order to answer the following research question: "What are the institutions and countries that either cite or are cited by the IRIS publications included in OpenCitations of 6 given Italian institutions (SNS, UNIBO, UNIMI, UNIPD, UNITO, UPO)?"

2.4.7 Software description

A Python pipeline for mapping Italian scientific citation networks across six universities (SNS, UNIBO, UNIMI, UNIPD, UNITO, UPO). The software processes ~350GB of bulk data exports from IRIS institutional repositories, OpenCitations, OpenAIRE, and ROR without relying on live API queries, streaming large archives directly to minimize disk usage. Four sequential scripts handle the full workflow: linking IRIS publication records to OpenCitations metadata, resolving affiliated organizations and countries via OpenAIRE and ROR, and aggregating incoming and outgoing citation counts per institution. All outputs are produced in open, non-proprietary formats (CSV, JSON) and the pipeline is designed for reproducibility, with idempotent execution and checkpoint/resume support for long-running stages.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

Yes

3.3.2 Ethical issues: description and solutions

The data processed by this software is drawn exclusively from publicly available open scholarly infrastructure sources (IRIS, OpenCitations, OpenAIRE, ROR), all of which are distributed under open licenses and intended for bulk reuse. No personal data is collected or processed. Since the pipeline operates entirely on pre-downloaded offline data dumps rather than querying live services, there is no risk of overloading external servers or violating API usage policies. No further ethical mitigation measures are required beyond compliance with the open licenses of the source datasets.

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

All created software will be preserved in a git repository and published on GitHub.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
Open Science 2025-26	https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026	No	No	Generalist

4.1.3 Further information on long-term preservation strategy

Software will be archived on Software Heritage and GitHub Archive Program automatically.

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20718139

4.2.2 Metadata

Basic software metadata will be provided alongside the repository: each pipeline stage automatically writes a machine-readable .metadata.json file recording runtime statistics (elapsed time, row counts, file sizes) for the corresponding output, providing provenance information that links each data output to the conditions under which it was produced.

4.2.3 Keywords

python, iris, opencitations, openaire, ror

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

All research outputs will be published on public GitHub and Zenodo repositories.

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

Data is collected by downloading bulk exports from open sources (IRIS, OpenCitations, OpenAIRE, ROR) and processed through a fixed four-stage sequential pipeline implemented in Python. Each stage reads the outputs of the previous one, applies deterministic transformation and cross-referencing logic, and writes structured intermediate or final outputs (CSV, JSON) alongside a

provenance record. Scripts are idempotent and support checkpoint/resume, so the pipeline can be safely interrupted and restarted without reprocessing completed work. The methodology is reproducible end-to-end: given the same input dumps, the pipeline will produce identical outputs. While the scripts are tightly coupled to the specific schemas of the current source datasets, the pipeline structure and logic can be adapted to updated dump formats or extended to additional institutions with targeted modifications.

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

The pipeline relies on established persistent identifier schemes throughout: DOIs (ISO 26324) and PMIDs for publication identification, OpenCitations Meta Identifiers (OMIDs) as the internal linking key across pipeline stages, OpenAIRE organization identifiers for affiliation edges, and ROR IDs (Research Organization Registry) for institution disambiguation and country resolution. Output data is serialized in CSV (RFC 4180) and JSON, both widely adopted, non-proprietary interchange formats. No domain-specific ontologies or taxonomies are applied beyond the identifier schemes natively used by the source datasets.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

other

Comment:

ISC

4.5.2 Documentation

A README.md file will be provided with a description of the project, the research question addressed, and instructions for setting up the environment and running the pipeline. Each pipeline stage additionally produces a .metadata.json file recording runtime statistics and output provenance. The source code itself is structured and commented to make the processing logic transparent and reproducible.

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

Quality is ensured through several complementary mechanisms. Each pipeline stage writes a .metadata.json file recording row counts, file sizes, and elapsed time, allowing verification that outputs are complete and consistent across runs. Scripts are idempotent and produce deterministic outputs given the same inputs, making it straightforward to detect regressions by re-running individual stages. Final outputs are reviewed manually to verify that citation counts and organization/country assignments are plausible against known institutional profiles.

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

Data is stored via git versioning on GitHub and published versions on Zenodo.

5.2.2 Backup

Data is preserved via git versioning on GitHub and published versions on Zenodo.

5.2.3 Additional security

No additional security: data processed is open and publicly accessible.

ROR data dump

The ROR data dump is a publicly available bulk export provided by the Research Organization Registry (ROR). Released as a ZIP archive containing a JSON file, it provides structured metadata for research organizations worldwide, including identifiers, names, types, and country information. In this pipeline it is used to resolve OpenAIRE organization IDs to their corresponding countries of operation.

Version used: 2.7 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>)

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Buttrick, Adam	0000-0003-1507-1031	adam@ror.org	ROR

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
Buttrick, Adam	0000-0003-1507-1031	adam@ror.org	ROR	

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

ROR

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

Yes

2.1.2 Re-using an existing dataset: why and how

The ROR dump provides authoritative country metadata for research organizations and is used to cross-reference OpenAIRE organization records, resolving each to a country of affiliation. ROR data is preferred over OpenAIRE's own country field where available, ensuring consistency through a widely adopted open standard.

The ROR dataset is published under CC0, placing it in the public domain with no restrictions on reuse.

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

ROR Data

2.2.2 Data types

- a. textual
- b. born digital
- c. raw
- d. qualitative

2.2.3 Data formats

- a. JSON
- b. CSV

2.2.4 Size of data

megabytes (MB)

Comment:

350

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

The ROR data dump is downloaded directly from the ROR website as a bulk export, released periodically as a versioned ZIP archive containing a JSON file with the full set of indexed research organizations and their metadata.

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

The ROR dump is used to resolve the country of affiliation for organizations linked to the publications identified in the IRIS-to-OpenCitations mapping dataset, fulfilling the location component of the research question.

2.2.7 Dataset description

A bulk dump of the Research Organization Registry (ROR), distributed as a JSON file under CC0, providing structured metadata for research organizations worldwide, including identifiers, names, and country of location. In this project it is

used to resolve the country of affiliation for organizations linked to publications in the IRIS-to-OpenCitations mapping dataset.

Version 2.7, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
ROR data	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273	Yes	No	Discipline specific

	73			
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4.1.3 Further information on long-term preservation strategy

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273

4.2.2 Metadata

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

4.2.3 Keywords

ROR, persistent identifier, organization identifier, PID, affiliation, open infrastructure, institution identifier

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

The ROR dump uses ROR IDs, a community-standard persistent identifier scheme for research organizations, and is distributed in JSON following ROR's openly documented schema. This allows direct cross-referencing with OpenAIRE organization records by identifier, ensuring interoperability between the two datasets without custom mapping tables.

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

The dataset uses ROR IDs, the community-standard persistent identifier scheme for research organizations, along with ISO 3166 country codes for location metadata.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/>

4.5.2 Documentation

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

5.2.2 Backup

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

5.2.3 Additional security

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140273>

OpenCitations data dump

OpenCitations Meta data dump is a dataset containing all the bibliographic metadata (in CSV format) involved in the citations indexed by the OpenCitations infrastructure, adhering to Open Science principles and published under a CC0 license to promote maximum reuse. Each line of the CSV file defines a bibliographic resource. As part of the BLOOM project, the team used version 13 of the dataset.

For additional information, please refer to the original dataset publication:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Peroni, Silvio	0000-0003-0530-4305	silvio.peroni@unibo.it	University of Bologna

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
Massari, Arcangelo	0000-0002-8420-0696	arcangelo.massari@unibo.it	OpenCitations	Data curator

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

University of Bologna

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

Yes

2.1.2 Re-using an existing dataset: why and how

As part of the BLOOM project, the OpenCitations Meta data dump is used to map the international reach of Italian academic research. It has been used for answering both first and second research question of the project. In particular, the data dump contains bibliographic metadata and persistent identifiers for publications indexed by OpenCitations, thus it is re-used (RQ 1A) to resolve OMIDs from the IRIS citation pairs into DOI, PMID, ISBN and publication date values; (RQ 1B) to gather citation relationships and venue metadata and create the omid-

venue mapping expanding the source dataset (available here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18202530>).

The dataset is licensed under CC0 (Creative Commons Zero), enabling unrestricted reuse.

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

OpenCitations Meta

2.2.2 Data types

- a. textual
- b. born digital
- c. qualitative
- d. derived

2.2.3 Data formats

csv

2.2.4 Size of data

gigabytes (GB)

Comment:

The compressed dataset weighs 13G, while, when extracted, it weighs 51G on an ext4 filesystem.

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

The data was not directly generated from the authors of the project, but rather downloaded from the OpenCitations infrastructure.

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation

(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

Data collection is necessary to fill a critical gap in the existing source dataset (available here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18202530>), which primarily contains records for the IRIS publications themselves. To answer the research question regarding the “Map of Italian Science”, we must retrieve missing metadata for the external entities that either cite or are cited by these publications.

2.2.7 Dataset description

The OpenCitations Meta dataset v. 13 includes "all the bibliographic metadata (in CSV format) included in OpenCitations Meta. Each line of the CSV file defines a bibliographic resource, and includes the following information:

- [field "id"] the IDs for the document described within the line;
- [field "title"] the document's title; - [field "author"] the authors of the document;
- [field "pub_date"] the date of publication;
- [field "venue"] information about the venue, i.e. the bibliographical resource to which the document belongs;
- [field "volume"] the volume sequence identifier (e.g. a number) to which the entity belongs;
- [field "issue"] the issue sequence identifier (e.g. a number) to which the entity belongs;
- [field "page"] the page range of the resource described in the row;
- [field "type"] the type of resource described in the row;
- [field "publisher"] the entity responsible for making the resource available;

- [field "editor"] the editors of the document.

This version of the dataset contains:

- 129,436,832 bibliographic entities
- 389,069,283 authors, 2,862,406 editors, and 106,791,171 publishers (counted by their roles, without disambiguating individual entities)
- 1,376,246 publication venues"

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your ouput? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your ouput?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537	Yes	Yes	Generalist

4.1.3 Further information on long-term preservation strategy

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
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	not yet available

4.2.2 Metadata

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

4.2.3 Keywords

Open Science, OpenCitations, Digital Humanities

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

The material is openly available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and on the official webpage (<https://download.opencitations.net/#meta>).

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/>

4.5.2 Documentation

Documentation of the OpenCitations Meta data dump is provided both on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and on the official repository (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

5.2.2 Backup

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

5.2.3 Additional security

For detailed information, please refer to the original journal article (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292) describing the OpenCitations Meta database, to the data dump documentation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324537>) and to the OpenCitations Meta documentation (https://opencitations.github.io/oc_meta/).

Alignment with LOC Categories

To ensure a consistent analysis of disciplinary citation flows, we rely on a pre-existing SKOS alignment dataset that maps multiple classification systems to the Library of Congress scheme. This dataset is crucial because disciplinary information retrieved from sources such as DOAJ and SCIMAGO is expressed using heterogeneous and non-interoperable classification systems. Direct comparison would therefore be unreliable. The alignment dataset provides a curated and semantically grounded mapping between these systems, built through a systematic comparison of journal classifications across multiple databases. By using this resource, we avoid performing a new alignment from scratch and ensure a higher level of consistency and reliability in the mapping process.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
De Dominicis, Ilenia	0009-0008-2026-5889	iliana.dedominicis2@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
Peroni, Silvio	https://orcid.org/0000-	silvio.peroni@u	University of	Researcher

	0003-0530-4305	nibo.it	Bologna	
Liggeri, Nicole	0009-0006-9417-2648	/	University of Bologna	Creator

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

Alma Mater Studiorum- Università di Bologna

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

Yes

2.1.2 Re-using an existing dataset: why and how

Our research concerns the alignment of the scholarly disciplines that either cites or are cited by the IRIS publications included in OpenCitations of a given institution. To ensure a consistent analysis of disciplinary citation flows, we rely on a pre-existing SKOS alignment dataset that maps heterogeneous classification systems (e.g. DOAJ and SCIMAGO) to the Library of Congress scheme.

There are no explicit restrictions for data reuse, since the aim of the dataset is to help other researchers with LOC alignment.

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

Allineamento SKOS alle categorie della Library of Congress

2.2.2 Data types

- a. textual
- b. born digital
- c. qualitative
- d. derived

2.2.3 Data formats

- a. csv
- b. ttl
- c. rdf

2.2.4 Size of data

megabytes (MB)

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

The data generation and alignment process is fully documented in:

<https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026/blob/main/bloom/categories/Documantazi%20one%20allineamento%20skos.pdf>

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

The dataset was created to identify and formalize correspondences between heterogeneous scientific classification systems across databases, enabling semantic alignment with the Library of Congress classification.

2.2.7 Dataset description

The dataset is organised into three main components:

A. LoC + alignments (RDF/XML): a set of RDF files representing Library of Congress (LoC) classification concepts enriched with semantic alignments (e.g. `skos:closeMatch`, `skos:narrowMatch`) to categories from other classification systems.

B. Original categories (CSV): a collection of CSV files describing the hierarchical structure (broad and narrow categories) of the original classification systems (e.g. Scopus).

C. SKOS vocabularies of external systems (TTL): a set of SKOS vocabularies, expressed in Turtle format, modelling the classification systems of external sources as structured concept schemes, derived from the original CSV data.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

The data we reuse are currently stored in a GitHub repository. Upon publication, we intend to deposit them in a permanent repository such as Zenodo, ensuring that they are accessible and citable as part of the resources used in this study, provided that the dataset owner agrees.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
open science	https://	No	No	Generalist

2025/2026	github.com/ open-sci/2025- 2026			
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4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20718139

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

The dataset can be found on GitHub:

<https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026/tree/main/bloom/categories>.

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

The methodology followed throughout the data lifecycle is described in this documentation published on GitHub:

<https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026/blob/main/bloom/categories/Documentazione%20allineamento%20skos.pdf>. The whole workflow can be also found here, in the README.md file: <https://github.com/NicoleLiggeri/intership-OC>.

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

The resulting dataset, aligned with the Library of Congress classification, is encoded in RDF, while the source vocabularies are serialized in Turtle (TTL) format.

The data are modeled using the SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) standard.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

other

Comment:

The dataset is available on GitHub; licensing terms follow the repository specifications.

4.5.2 Documentation

The documentation is provided at this GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026/blob/main/bloom/categories/Documantazi%20allineamento%20skos.pdf>. Other specifications about the project workflow are found here: <https://github.com/NicoleLiggeri/intership-OC>.

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

The data are modeled using the SKOS standard, ensuring a controlled and consistent representation of concepts, labels, and relationships across the dataset.

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

Access to the dataset is granted via this GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026>. Access is granted to collaborators through GitHub permissions (e.g., repository access roles), ensuring controlled access to the data. All changes are tracked via Git versioning, which records contributions, revisions, and timestamps, enabling transparency and accountability in collaborative work.

5.2.2 Backup

Data are stored locally and regularly backed up via a GitHub repository, which provides version control and off-site storage. In case of data loss, files can be recovered from the repository or from local backups.

Public Journals in the DOAJ database

The Journal CSV provides a full list of all public journals in the DOAJ database.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Yang, Tianchi	0009-0006-6945-0781	tianchi.yang@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna
Nakamura, Shiho	0009-0001-8829-8643	shiho.nakamura@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
DOAJ	-	helpdesk@doaj.org	DOAJ	Creator

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

ALMA MATER STUDIORIUM - University of Bologna

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

Yes

2.1.2 Re-using an existing dataset: why and how

To gather information of disciplines (subjects) of journals from the DOAJ database, in order to analyze disciplinary flow of scholarly citations of Italian Universities.

It is a public dataset.

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

Journal CSV

2.2.2 Data types

- a. textual
- b. born digital
- c. secondary

2.2.3 Data formats

csv

2.2.4 Size of data

megabytes (MB)

Comment:

23.69

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

Data is collected through online applications submitted by journal publishers. DOAJ's editorial team reviews and verifies this information before it is added to the database. Further information can be found here: <https://doaj.org/apply/guide/>

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

The data was collected to support the discovery, accessibility, and transparency of open access scholarly journals worldwide.

2.2.7 Dataset description

This dataset is a journal-level metadata collection provided by the Directory of Open Access Journals in CSV format. It contains structured information about open access academic journals worldwide.

The dataset includes 52 variables describing different aspects of each journal. These variables cover general information (such as journal title, ISSN, publisher, and country), access and licensing details (e.g., journal license, copyright policies, and open access compliance), editorial and review processes, publication fees (APC), and preservation services. It also includes metadata related to indexing and activity, such as subjects, keywords, number of article records, and dates of updates.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

Not applicable as the preservation of this dataset will be handled directly by DOAJ. The copy we will use for our research will be preserved on our Github repository, as is, with no changes to the data.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
Open Science 2025-2026	https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026	No	No	Generalist

4.1.3 Further information on long-term preservation strategy

DOAJ runs JASPER (JournAIs are Preserved forevER), an initiative to preserve open access journals. Journal publishers, under the statement that “Open access journals must be preserved forever” Further information can be found here: <https://doaj.org/preservation/>

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20718139

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

DOAJ supports multiple interoperable access formats: CSV, XML, JSON (via API), and OAI-PMH. The data is also incorporated into commercial discovery systems, library discovery portals and search engines

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

DOAJ uses the LCC (Library of Congress Classification) for subject categorization. It also requires standard identifiers like ISSNs and DOIs.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/>

4.5.2 Documentation

The primary documentation is the CSV header row, which defines each of the 50+ metadata fields. Additionally, DOAJ provides a public API guide (<https://doaj.org/api/v4/docs>) and a blog, and a metadata FAQ page. (<https://doaj.org/docs/faq/>)

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

Quality is ensured through a process including a strict criteria. Journals must meet "The Principles of Transparency and Best Practice in Scholarly Publishing". Data is also subject to community reporting and periodic re-evaluation to ensure journals still meet standard.

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Other

Comment:

No documents or descriptions that currently explain the storage solution of the dataset could be found. For the purpose of developing the BLOOM project, the downloaded dataset will be stored in a GitHub repository, tracked through logs and version history.

5.2.2 Backup

Same as above. In addition, as the data is also distributed via the API and CSV to thousands of libraries worldwide, the community effectively acts as a secondary distributed backup.

Scimago Journal Subject Areas and Categories

This dataset is directly downloaded from <https://www.scimagojr.com/journalrank.php>, which is a list of all journals metadata in SCImago Journal Rank, ranked by the SJR (a measure of journals impact, influence or prestige).

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Manyara, Regina	0009-0007-6773-3910	regina.wkmanyara@gmail.com	University of Bologna
Li, Yi Hua	0009-0005-9325-0328	e62565897@gmail.com	University of Bologna

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
SCImago	-	contact@scimago.es	Scopus®	Creator

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

University of Bologna

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

Time spent planning how to fulfill each guideline.

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

Yes

2.1.2 Re-using an existing dataset: why and how

We are reusing the dataset downloaded from Scimago which contains metadata information about scholarly journals. For our research purposes we will make use of the following columns -

Title;Type;Issn;Publisher;Country;Region;Coverage;Categories;Areas

The data will be processed and cleaned using python and related libraries such as Pandas

SCImago, (n.d.). SJR-SCImago Journal Country & Rank [Portal]. Retrieved (Date), from <https://www.scimagojr.com>

The pandas development team. (2026). pandas-dev/pandas: Pandas (v3.13). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19340003>

All the information shown in the SCImago Journal Country & Rank website can be used for non-commercial purposes as long as it is cited.

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

scimago

2.2.2 Data types

- a. Textual
- b. Born Digital
- c. Qualitative

2.2.3 Data formats

csv

2.2.4 Size of data

megabytes (MB)

Comment:

11.3

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

The methodology employed by Scimago is described here:

<https://www.scimagojr.com/methodology.php>

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

The dataset will provide the necessary scholarly discipline information we need to understand the disciplinary flow of the IRIS institutions.

2.2.7 Dataset description

The dataset will aggregate all the journals available in Scimago that correspond to the journals in the iris_oc mapping of scholarly information.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

Not applicable as the preservation of this dataset will be handled directly by Scimago. The copy we will use for our research will be preserved on our Github repository, as is, with no changes to the data.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
open-sci	https://	No	No	Generalist

	github.com/ open-sci/2025- 2026/blob/ a9e9e23e5f01b e746257d61da2 a6e4ae3de61a4 7/bloom/ disciplinary_flo w/ journal_data/ scimago.csv			
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4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20718139

4.2.2 Metadata

The Scimago data dump did not provide metadata on download.

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

The data is available on the Scimago website at - <https://www.scimagojr.com>

The version saved in the project's Github repository is available at - https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026/blob/a9e9e23e5f01be746257d61da2a6e4ae3de61a47/bloom/disciplinary_flow/journal_data/scimago.csv

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

No

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

Scimago uses the international standard for the identification of bibliographic venues - i.e issn, which allows it to be aligned to other scholarly databases

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

This information can be found in the Scimago methodology
<https://www.scimagojr.com/methodology.php>

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

other

Comment:

All the information shown in the SCImago Journal Country & Rank website can be used for non-commercial purposes as long as it is cited.

4.5.2 Documentation

The dataset it made available and visualised on the Scimago website.

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

This information can be found in the Scimago methodology
<https://www.scimagojr.com/methodology.php>

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Institutional internal Server

5.2.2 Backup

This information can be found in the Scimago methodology

<https://www.scimagojr.com/methodology.php>

Flow of Scholarly Domains of IRIS_OC Institutions

This dataset is the aggregation of the IRIS_OC_index citation data with the subjecting information from external data dumps (DOAJ and Scimago) aligned with LOC subject classifications for the purpose of investigating the disciplinary flow of IRIS_OC publications

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Manyara, Regina	0009-0007-6773-3910	regina.wkmanyara@gmail.com	University of Bologna

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
Manyara, Regina	0009-0007-6773-3910	regina.wkmanyara@gmail.com	University of Bologna	Creator
Nakamura, Shiho	0009-0001-8829-8643	shiho.nakamura@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator
De Dominicis,	0009-0008-	ilaria.dedominic	University of	Creator

Ilaria	2026-5889	is2@studio.unibo.it	Bologna	
Yang, Tianchi	0009-0006-6945-0781	yangtianchi2017@gmail.com	University of Bologna	Creator
Li, Yi Hua	0009-0005-9325-0328	e62565897@gmail.com	University of Bologna	Creator
Ak, Yiğit	0009-0002-0852-3896	yigit.ak@studio.unibo.it	University of Bologna	Creator
Chen, Qinghao	0009-0000-9290-0222	luyihehu@gmail.com	University of Bologna	Creator

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

University of Bologna

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

Time spent planning how to fulfill each guideline.

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

No

2.1.3 Creating a new dataset

The dataset is original as there was no other available dataset specifically addressing the research question.

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

BLOOM-IRIS_OC-Disciplinary_Flow

2.2.2 Data types

- a. textual
- b. born digital
- c. derived

2.2.3 Data formats

csv

2.2.4 Size of data

gigabytes (GB)

Comment:

17

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

This dataset will make use of the DOAJ scholarly category dataset, Scimago category dataset and the LOC classifications to align the subjects and categories of the IRIS_OC publications

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

To investigate the disciplinary flow of Italian research

2.2.7 Dataset description

The BLOOM IRIS_OC Disciplinary Flow dataset traces the flow of scholarly disciplines between the citations of the research from IRIS, a group of six Italian universities (UNIBO, UNIMI, UNITO, UNIPD, UPO, and SNS). The dataset extends

the iris_in_oc_index dataset with venue information from the OpenCitations Meta data dump in order to further expand the data with the scholarly disciplinary information of two external data dumps, DOAJ and Scimago. To provide a standard description of all scholarly disciplines an alignment was created with the LOC subject classification. The primary output will be a csv file for human-readability and an RDF turtle file for possible interoperability with other linked open data (like OpenCitation). This dataset will be used to investigate the following research question: what are the scholarly disciplines that either cite or are cited by the IRIS publications included in OpenCitations of a given institution?

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

The entirety of the dataset can be preserved as it is.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?

Data for the article "In the World of Citations, Are We Really Open(Minded), or Stuck in a Comfort Zone?" Authors/Creators	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2069155	Yes	Yes	Generalist
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4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20691555

4.2.2 Metadata

The metadata will be provided after the creation of the complete dataset

4.2.3 Keywords

Open Science, Digital Humanities, Bibliometrics

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

The full dataset will be made available on Zenodo as well as on the Github repository of the project

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

Step 1: Retrieve venue data using OC Meta data dumps

Step 2: Use venue PIDs (e.g. issn) to extract subject info from external data dumps (DOAJ and Scimago)

Step 3: Use LOC classifications to align and standardise subjects across all iris_oc resources

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

Library of Congress subject classification

SCOPUS subject classification

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

4.5.2 Documentation

The dataset will be documented by README files, a notebook file and the final paper.

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

Data quality is guaranteed by a structured workflow and reciprocal reviews performed by the research group members.

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

The scripts and interim datasets used during the workflow will be made available on Github. While the full resulting dataset will be published and stored on Zenodo

5.2.2 Backup

Github

OpenAIRE data dump

The OpenAIRE Graph (v10.6.0) is an open scholarly knowledge graph produced and maintained by OpenAIRE, aggregating metadata about research products, organisations, projects, and their interrelationships from thousands of open data sources worldwide. It is distributed as tar archives of gzip-compressed JSON files on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/17725827>).

For this project, three specific subsets of the v10.6.0 dump were downloaded and processed: publication records, relation records (including affiliation links between publications and organisations), and organisation records. The organisation dump was used to map OpenAIRE organisation identifiers to ROR identifiers, enabling country-level geographic attribution. All other dump subsets (datasets, software, projects, communities) were not used.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Paolo Manghi	0000-0001-7291-3210	paolo.manghi@openaire.eu	OpenAIRE

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
Claudio Atzori	0000-0001-9613-6639	claudio.atzori@isti.cnr.it	OpenAIRE	

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

OpenAIRE

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/records/17725827>.

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

Yes

2.1.2 Re-using an existing dataset: why and how

The OpenAIRE Graph dataset was reused to map research publications to their authors' institutional affiliations and geographic locations. Specifically:

- the **publication** and **relation** dumps were used to link research outputs to their affiliated organisations via PIDs;

- the **organisation** dump was used to resolve OpenAIRE organisation identifiers to ROR identifiers, enabling the extraction of country-level information.

The original dataset is produced and maintained by OpenAIRE and licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

OpenAIRE Graph Dataset

2.2.2 Data types

- a. textual
- b. born digital
- c. qualitative
- d. raw

2.2.3 Data formats

json

2.2.4 Size of data

gigabytes (GB)

Comment:

330.8

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

The data was not generated by the project team. It was downloaded directly from the OpenAIRE Graph dump (v10.6.0) available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17725827>.

For this project, the following specific subsets of the dump were downloaded and processed: publication dumps, relation dumps and organisation dump.

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

This dataset was reused to map research publications to their authors' institutional affiliations and geographic locations. The publication and relation dumps were processed to link research outputs to their affiliated organisations via persistent identifiers. The organisation dump was used to resolve OpenAIRE organisation identifiers to ROR identifiers, enabling country-level geographic attribution. All other dump subsets were not used.

2.2.7 Dataset description

The **OpenAIRE Graph** (v10.6.0) is one of the largest open scholarly record collections worldwide. It aggregates metadata about research products (publications, datasets, software, and other outputs), organisations, projects, and their interrelationships, drawn from thousands of trusted data sources including institutional repositories, journal publishers, and funding agencies.

The v10.6.0 dump used in this project was released on 1 December 2025. The dump is structured as several tar archives containing gzip-compressed files, each with one JSON record per line, conforming to the schema available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14608526>.

For this project, the following specific subsets of the dump were downloaded and processed:

- **Publication dumps** (14 tar archives): metadata records for research literature, used to map publications to their authors' institutional affiliations via persistent identifiers.

- **Relation dumps** (14 tar archives): records describing relationships between entities (e.g. publication–organisation links), used to extract affiliation relationships between research outputs and resolved organisations.

- **Organisation dump** (1 tar archive): metadata records for organisations, used to map OpenAIRE organisation identifiers to ROR (Research Organization Registry) identifiers, enabling country-level geographic attribution

Dataset dumps not relevant to this analysis were not downloaded.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/17725827>.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
OpenAIRE Graph Dataset	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17725827	Yes	No	Discipline specific

4.1.3 Further information on long-term preservation strategy

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/17725827>.

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17725827

4.2.2 Metadata

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/17725827>.

4.2.3 Keywords

Open Science, Scholarly Communication, Information Science

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/records/17725827>.

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

The OpenAIRE Graph data model (v10.6.0, documented at <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/data-model/>) structures the graph around six main entity types — Research Products, Organisations, Data Sources, Projects, Communities, and Persons — and the relationships between them. Records are distributed as gzip-compressed JSON files conforming to the schema available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4238938>. For this project, three entity types were relevant: Research Product records, Relation records and Organisation records.

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

A detailed report on the OpenAIRE Graph Data Model can be found at <https://zenodo.org/records/2643199>.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Comment:

The OpenAIRE Graph dump is licensed under CC BY 4.0. Appropriate attribution to the original OpenAIRE Graph dataset must be provided when reusing this data: Manghi, P., Atzori, C., Bardi, A., Baglioni, M., Dimitropoulos, H., La Bruzzo, S., Fofoulas, I., Mannocci, A., Horst, M., Iatropoulou, K., Kokogiannaki, A., De Bonis, M., Artini, M., Lempeis, A., Ioannidis, A., Manola, N., Principe, P., Vergoulis, T., & Chatzopoulos, S. (2025). OpenAIRE Graph Dataset (10.6.0) [Data set]. OpenAIRE.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17725827>

4.5.2 Documentation

Refer to the OpenAIRE Graph documentation at <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/>.

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/records/17725827>.

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/records/17725827>.

5.2.2 Backup

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/records/17725827>.

5.2.3 Additional security

Refer to the original dataset publication on Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/records/17725827>.

Software for enriching and extending IRIS_OC data for RQ 1b

This software is used to enrich and extend the IRIS_OC citation data, merging the relevant information from the OpenCitation, DOAJ and Scimago datadumps and mapping the resulting dataset with the Library of Congress subject alignments.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Manyara, Regina	0009-0007-6773-3910	regina.wkmanyara@gmail.com	University of Bologna

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
Li, Yi Hua	0009-0005-9325-0328	e62565897@gmail.com	University of Bologna	Creator

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1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

University of Bologna

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

Time spent planning how to fulfill each guideline.

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Software

2 Summary

2.3 Identification of software

2.3.1 Are you re-using already existing software?

No

2.3.3 Creating new software

We will need to create our own software for handling the specific requirements of our research question, namely:

- Extracting venue data from OpenCitation Meta data dump
- Merging and aggregating the internal (iris_oc) citation dataset and external (DOAJ and Scimago) datasets
- Mapping and aligning subject, category and area information to LOC classifications

2.4 Software characteristics

2.4.1 Software name

Disciplinary_Flow

2.4.2 Type of software

application software

2.4.3 Software formats

.py

2.4.4 Size of software

megabytes (MB)

Comment:

52

2.4.5 How is software created/used

The software will be created using python and will make use of available libraries and packages necessary for the management, cleaning, expansion and visualisation of the research data.

2.4.6 Why is the software created/used

The software is created in order to parse through the OpenCitation Meta data dump combine the resulting data with the internal (iris_oc) and external (DOAJ and Scimago) datasets, align the subjects to LOC classifications and visualise the resulting dataset in order to answer the research question: "What are the scholarly disciplines that that either cites or are cited by the IRIS publications included in OpenCitations of a given institution?"

2.4.7 Software description

The software will be made of several different python scripts each tasked with handling one of the steps in the workflow of the research.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

The software will be made available on a Github repository and preserved on Zenodo

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
open science 2025/2026	https://github.com/open-sci/2025-2026	No	No	Generalist

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20718139

Comment:

Not yet available

4.2.2 Metadata

Basic software metadata will be provided: authors, date of creation, date of modification, license.

4.2.3 Keywords

opencitation, bibliometrics, doaj, scimago

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

The software and accompanying metadata will be made available through Github.

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

The methodology will be described in all the python files of the software as comments, making explainable and understandable to future users.

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

library of congress, skos, relevant SPAR ontologies

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

MIT, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MIT_License

4.5.2 Documentation

A README.md file with the description and usage instruction will be provided.

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

Quality will be assessed through automated tests and review of produced data

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

The software will be preserved via git versioning on GitHub.

5.2.2 Backup

Data is preserved via git versioning on GitHub.

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